

This document is the Accepted Manuscript version of a Published Work after peer review and technical editing by the publisher that appeared in final form in [Journal of Chromatography A, 1620 (2020) 461007], To access the final edited and published work see [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2020.461007].

Supercritical fluid chromatography separation of chiral pesticides: Unique capabilities to study cyhalothrin and metalaxyl as examples

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ABSTRACT

Evaluation of chiral pesticides remains a frequently neglected matter in routine food control laboratories. This fact is due to the existence of many residue definitions but also due to the lack of robust instrumental methods for the evaluation of these isomeric compounds. However, supercritical fluid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (SFC-ESI-MS/MS) has been demonstrated to perform fast and highly efficient separations without the need to change the mobile phase employed in multiresidue pesticide analyses. Regarding chiral stationary phase columns, the polysaccharide-based ones clearly demonstrate the best separation technology. Two polysaccharide-based columns were tested in this study, and the robustness of their combination with SFC was verified. The enantiomers of lambda-cyhalothrin and metalaxyl were studied precisely due to their markedly distinct toxicity and enantioselectivity. Furthermore, the acute reference dose for gamma-cyhalothrin is half in comparison with its enantiomer (0.0025 and 0.005 mg/kg respectively), which is present in the lambda-cyhalothrin residue definition. These enantiomers were analyzed in terms of linearity, reproducibility, and matrix effects in four representative matrices (tomato, orange, leek, and cayenne). Additionally, field tests under greenhouse conditions for these compounds were performed. The results obtained after different sample collections revealed a similar degradation in lambda-cyhalothrin enantiomers (R, S, S, and S, R, R) but not in the case of metalaxyl-M (mefenoxam) where the degradation in tomato was 2 to 6 times less in comparison with its S-enantiomer.

Keywords: Supercritical fluid chromatograph; Enantiomeric separation; Pesticides; Chiral stationary phases

1. Introduction

Separation of enantiomers is a well-known practice in pharmaceutical industry [1]. Enantioseparation of some pharmaceuticals is mandatory to launch enantiopure drugs into the market. However, enantioseparation of pesticides, despite the proven enantioselectivity present in nature -and unlike pharmaceutical compounds- is a complex field thoroughly. Different pesticides, belonging to varying chemical classes, can cause stronger or weaker interactions with the active site within an organism due to their different isomer spatial conformation [2]. As pesticides improve the productivity and profitability of agricultural products, their use has increased considerably in the United States and the European Union. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a proper analytical method to identify of chiral pesticides and to understand their degradation mechanism in food applications.

Many examples of pesticide enantioselectivity exist. Fipronil, for instance, demonstrates apparent enantioselective degradation in sediments. As a consequence, one isomer is bioaccumulated at higher concentrations in blackworm tissue than the other [3]. S-fipronil has also been found to affect more intensely the DNA methylation of genes related to neurological processes in zebrafish [4]. On the other hand, each paclobutrazol enantiomer presented effects of different magnitude in the photosynthetic pigments and transcriptions in *C.vulgaris* algae [5]. Benalaxyl and metalaxyl isomers have enantioselectivity effects that influence DNA methylation [6].

It has been demonstrated that the metalaxyl isomer metalaxyl-M (mefenoxam), is the most effective enantiomer [7]. This pesticide is of great interest and hence research on its enantioselectivity is abundant, for example, the enantioselective dissipation process in soil matrix [8]. different superoxide dismutase activities in tobacco plants [9]. enhanced metalaxyl-M persistence in olive-mill waste amended soils [10]. and the different influence of each enantiomer on metabolic pathway disturbance in rats [11]. Like most pesticides (except lambda-cyhalothrin), metalaxyl enantiomers have the same ARfD (0.5 mg/kg) [12]. Moreover, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) uses the same toxicological endpoints for metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M, and an analytical method for the enantioseparation of both enantiomers is also described in one of their reports [13].

Lambda-cyhalothrin is a pyrethroid (a pyrethrin derivate) and one of the

diastereomeric pair of enantiomers in cyhalothrin [14]. The popularity of pyrethroids is increasing. Nonetheless, it is a known fact that these compounds can be toxic to mammals [15]. and there are several studies similar to those performed on metalaxyl, such as the one looking at their different ecotoxicological effects in zebrafish [16]. However, it is the different acute reference dose (ARfD) for each enantiomer of the lambda-cyhalothrin pair which makes it more significant. The ARfD for gamma-cyhalothrin (the S,R,R isomer) is 0.0025 mg/kg whereas the ARfD of its enantiomer (R,S,S) is 0.005 mg/kg. Therefore, the gamma-cyhalothrin enantiomer is twice as toxic as its enantiomer; accordingly, and it is essential to achieve good chromatographic separation and validation of both isomers in food analysis. All these factors are of potential relevance to European regulatory bodies given that continuous modifications to the maximum residue level for this compound are being implemented [17,18].

To obtain good separation, supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC) coupled to tandem mass spectrometry was applied in this study. Chiral analysis and purification are considered as one of the most dominant SFC applications in the pharmaceutical industry [19]. It is already known that SFC has many advantages, for instance, lower solvent consumption, shorter run times, lower matrix effects and improved ionization efficiency [20]. However, one of its many qualities is its ability to perform fast chiral separations with excellent resolution. The diffusivity in SFC is higher than in liquid chromatography (LC) so faster separations can be performed without compromising efficiency [21,22]. These attributes make SFC an excellent technique for preparative chromatography [23–25]. Regarding the mobile phase in LC, it is usually necessary to modify it substantially when a chiral separation is performed with polysaccharide columns. However, in SFC, the same mobile phase is commonly used for chiral separations and achiral column multiresidue methods.

There are a wide variety of chiral stationary phases (CSP) classified depending on their chemical composition. Polysaccharide chiral stationary phases are the most widely used CSP across all the chromatographic fields [26,27]. Polysaccharide phases can be derivatized at the active -OH groups, the carbamate form being the most popular. Cellulose-based and amylose-based chiral phases offer the possibility to interact with the analytes through the hydrogen bonds. Extensive research is being conducted on the structure of these stationary phases, since their mechanism of interaction with the analytes

is still quite ambiguous. The high complexity of these stationary phases allows the separation of a considerable number of compounds [28].

The main objective of the present work is to achieve the maximum number of enantiomeric pesticide separations using SFC-ESI-MS/MS. In order to highlight the advantages of this approach, a multiresidue method was created containing 21 pesticides. Four matrices containing a broad complex range were analyzed (tomato, orange, leek, cayenne). Particular attention was given to lambda-cyhalothrin and metalaxyl isomers, including field tests inside a greenhouse.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

Two different manufacturers provide the pesticide standards used in this study: Sigma Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany) and LGC (Teddington, United Kingdom). All the standards had a purity higher than 96% except for flucythrinate (87.5%). The analytical standards were stored at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The standard-mix solution was prepared using individual stock solutions. Individual stock solutions (around 1000 mgL^{-1}) were prepared from each standard and stored in the dark at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in amber glass vials.

Carbon dioxide (CO_2) was supplied by Air Liquide (Madrid, Spain), LC-MS quality methanol used for the preparation of the mobile phase was obtained from Fluka Analytical (Steinheim, Germany). The additives: ammonium formate and formic acid were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. The salts employed in the QuEChERS extraction (anhydrous magnesium sulphate, sodium chloride, sodium hydrogenocitrate sesquihydrate and sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany) except for the primary secondary amine salt (PSA) that was obtained from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA).

2.2. Sample preparation

Four representative matrices with different matrix compositions were obtained from a local market in Almeria (Spain). These matrices (tomato, orange, leek and cayenne) were extracted by citrate buffer QuEChERS with PSA dispersive solid-phase extraction (dSPE) clean-up and analyzed to ensure that they did not have any detectable pesticide of the ones present in our multiresidue method. The procedure

followed for the extraction did not have any modification and its parameters have been previously described. The final extract resulting from the extraction method contained 1 g of matrix per mL.

2.3. Vials preparation

The injection vials were prepared by evaporating 100 μ L of each blank extract under a gentle stream of nitrogen and reconstituting it with the same volume of acetonitrile containing the mixture of the analyzed pesticides at the desired concentration level. For the analysis of the field test samples, 100 μ L of each extract were introduced in a microvolume glass insert inside the vial.

2.4. SFC-MS/MS analysis

The SFC analysis was performed using a Nexera UC (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). In addition to the common devices of LC (binary pumps, column oven and autosampler), this system is equipped with a CO₂ pump and a back-pressure regulator (BPR) splitless device just before the MS source.

A modifier consisting of methanol with 1 mM Ammonium formate was mixed with the carbon dioxide. The make-up solvent used after the column was methanol containing 5 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid. The make-up solvent was introduced in the system isocratically at 0.080 mL min⁻¹. The SFC separation was carried out on a cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate) CSP column Lux® Cellulose-1 (5 μ m, 250 \times 4.6 mm) manufactured by Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). The other column tested in this study was the Lux® Amylose-3 (5 μ m, 250 \times 4.6 mm) also supplied by Phenomenex. The oven temperature was set at 40 °C. The BPR pressure and temperature were established at 150 bar and 50 °C respectively. The total flow used was kept constant at 1.5 mL min⁻¹ and the gradient was as follows: From 0 to 13 min, modifier flow was increased from 2% to 15% and from 13 to 13,5 min to 30%. This 30% of modifier was maintained for 2 min. The modifier percentage was then reduced from 30% to 2% to recover initial conditions and maintained over 2 min. Autosampler temperature was set at 15 °C and 2 μ L were established as the injection volume.

The SFC system is coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer LCMS 8060 (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). The study was carried out employing an

electrospray ionization source (ESI) operating with 5 ms of switching polarity time. The interface temperature was set at 300 °C, 250 °C for desolvation line and 400 °C in the case of heat block. The interface voltage used was 4 kV. Regarding nebulizer, heating and drying gas flows: 3 L min⁻¹, 10 L min⁻¹ and 10 L min⁻¹ were used respectively.

2.5. Optimization of the SFC-MS/MS parameters

The Shimadzu Extended multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) Library was used for the creation of the multiresidue method. This feature contains data of many transitions for each pesticide; three of them were selected following the sensitivity rank. Individual standard solutions of the pesticides were injected to confirm the transition with higher signal (quantifier) and the second most sensitive (qualifier). Some compounds such as internal standards (dimethoate-d6, carbendazim-d3, malathion-d10, and dichlorvos- d6) were not present in the library and must be manually optimized using precursor ion search. For a proper identification, two transitions must be detected with an ion ratio difference lower than 30% and a retention time shift under 0.1 min. Acquisition windows of ± 0.35 min were established for each pesticide isomer in the multiresidue method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Enantiomeric separation of pesticides

Two polysaccharide-based CSP were tested: cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate) and amylose tris(3-chloro-5-methylphenylcarbamate). Both had the same length (250 × 4.6 mm) and the same particle size. The composition of the mobile phases and flows remain the same as those in our previous studies of pesticide residue analysis using SFC-ESI-MS/MS [29]. A gradient was created with the aim of separating the highest number of chiral pesticides. Twenty-one pesticides were analyzed: iprovalicarb, metalaxyl, lambda-cyhalothrin, tetramethrin, fipronil, acephate, benalaxyl, phenothrin, cyfluthrin, methamidophos, flucythrinate, tau-fluvalinate, paclobutrazol, cypermethrin, penconazole, imazalil, fenvalerate, zoxamide, fenarimol, metconazole, and mandipropamid. Better results and shorter multiresidue runs were obtained with the cellulose column. Some

compounds like iprovalicarb, cyfluthrin, cypermethrin, fenarimol, fenvalerate, and mandipropamid could not be detected with the amylose column, perhaps because their elution is higher than the 18 min of our gradient. Furthermore, some compounds were not well separated, and just one peak showed in the chromatogram (methamidophos, flucythrinate, imazalil and metconazole). Fig. 1. displays the chromatograms of the compounds that this study intends to focus on closely (lambda-cyhalothrin and metalaxyl) using each CSP column. Applying the amylose CSP column, lambda-cyhalothrin elutes 3 min earlier than when using the cellulose CSP column. but the lambda-cyhalothrin enantiomeric separation is not very pronounced. With the metalaxyl mixture, the situation is similar: they elute later but the isomeric separation is not efficient. The chromatogram for the separation of enantiomers using the cellulose column with this multi-residue method can be observed in Fig. 2. Tetramethrin, cypermethrin, and cyfluthrin are compounds with a many isomers. Using this multiresidue method, they cannot be completely separated. A specific gradient is necessary to efficiently separate all their isomers. One of the advantages of SFC-ESI-MS/MS in pesticide analysis is the ionization efficiency - a consequence of the low flow reaching the source and the absence of water. This sampling efficiency increases the sensitivity of some chemical classes such as pyrethroids [29]. Eight of the twenty-one pesticides included in the multi-residue method were pyrethroids. This type of chromatography also allows the efficient separation of the pesticide enantiomers in 18 mins. A column change is the only step needed to transform the standard multiresidue method into a chiral one. Moreover, after 200 injections, the applied methodology remains efficient without any time shifting or peak shape degradation.

Cyhalothrin is a synthetic pyrethroid with 16 possible isomeric forms of 8 diastereomers. This pesticide is produced only in the *Z* and *cis* forms, reducing the number of isomers to 4. There is a pair with *S, S, S*, and *R, R, R* enantiomers and its diastereomeric pair with *R, S, S*, and *S, R, R* [30]. The two enantiomeric components of each pair cannot be separated with non-chiral chromatography. The chromatogram in Fig. 3. shows that, by applying a small variation in the method's elution gradient (8% of modifier at 15 min), one is able to separate the four cyhalothrin enantiomers. However, the application of this pesticide as a commercial formulation is not approved by the European Commission. Nonetheless, one of the diastereomeric pairs, lambda-cyhalothrin (*R, S, S*, and *S, R, R*), is not prohibited; it is especially interesting because the ARfD of the gamma

enantiomer (*S,R,R*) (ARfD: 0.0025 mg/kg) is only half that of its enantiomer (*R,S,S*) (ARfD: 0.005 mg/kg). The separation of the gamma-cyhalothrin from its enantiomer can be performed using the multiresidue method. Focusing on the other pesticides, some of them like benalaxyl, fipronil, paclobutrazol, or metalaxyl present enantioselectivity in nature, as mentioned in the Introduction section. Metalaxyl is the other pesticide analyzed precisely in this work. The ratio of metalaxyl to its isomers is approximately 1:1 but the isomeric degradation does not follow the same path. The next subsections will focus on the study of the lambda-cyhalothrin mixture and metalaxyl/metalaxyl-M (mefenoxam) in terms of linearity, reproducibility, and matrix effect. The identification was performed by acquiring specific standards of each isomer, gamma-cyhalothrin, and mefenoxam. Both compounds with their enantiomers were identified at 5 µg/Kg in the four matrices studied (tomato, orange, leek and cayenne). To thoroughly complete the study, a field test was applied by spiking both pesticides in different matrices inside a greenhouse.

3.2. Linearity

In order to study the linearity of the lambda-cyhalothrin and metalaxyl enantiomers, matrix-matched calibration curves were prepared at 5 different concentration levels (5, 10, 20, 100, and 500 µg/kg) in the four studied matrices. All the calibration curves showed a determination coefficient (r^2) higher than 0.99. Regarding the lambda-cyhalothrin enantiomers, very similar area values were obtained, and calibration curves were extremely similar to each other, except in the case of the orange matrix. The *R,S,S*-enantiomer showed lower area values in this matrix than the gamma enantiomer. This is related to the matrix effect (see [SubSection 3.3](#)). Nevertheless, the linearity of the calibration curve for lambda-cyhalothrin in the orange matrix provided a determination coefficient of 0.999. If we focus on metalaxyl and mefenoxam, the calibration curves in tomato and orange are very similar for both isomers, with greater differences in cayenne and leek, although they still fulfilled the linearity requirements.

3.3. Reproducibility

The lowest concentration levels (5 and 10 µg/kg) were selected for the

reproducibility studies. The method's reproducibility was calculated from five injections of each matrix sample extract. The results are listed in [Table 1](#). Both compounds and their isomers met the RSD requirements lower than 20% at 5 and 10 µg/kg. However, gamma-cyhalothrin and its enantiomer showed an RSD of 3% and 2% in tomato, 3% and 3% in orange, 12% and 13% in leek, and 12% and 9% in cayenne, respectively. The results for leek and cayenne satisfy the requirements but are slightly high. On the other hand, at 10 µg/kg, the RSD was below 4% in all the studied matrices. Focusing on the metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M 5 µg/kg reproducibility test, as with metalaxyl in the orange matrix, the RSD was over 10% (12%). Better results were obtained at the 10 µg/Kg concentration with an RSD range of between 2–8% for both isomers in all matrices, with just one exception, metalaxyl in orange showed an RSD result of 10%.

3.4. Matrix effect

Interfering matrix compounds can affect each isomer differently as they elute at different retention times. These compounds can co-elute with the analytes producing signal suppression or signal enhancement. Commonly, the interfering compounds produce signal suppression when ESI sources are used. However, the behavior of SFC is different, and its ionization benefits usually provide a reduction in the matrix effect. A matrix effect in the range of 0 to 20% is considered a non-existent or low matrix effect; however, alterations of the signal between 20 and 50% and >50% are considered medium and strong matrix effects, respectively.

As shown in [Table 2](#). Metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M exhibited matrix effects between -1 and 5% for both enantiomers. Therefore, it can be affirmed that there were no matrix effects when analyzing the metalaxyl enantiomers in the four studied matrices. Regarding the lambda-cyhalothrin enantiomers, they showed low matrix effects in tomato (*R,S,S*: -11%, gamma: -6%) and cayenne (*R,S,S*: 12%, gamma: 16%). However, the signal suppression in leek was -28% for the *R,S,S* enantiomer of lambda-cyhalothrin and -27% for gamma-cyhalothrin, which is considered a moderate matrix effect.

The situation in the orange matrix was slightly worst, with matrix effect values of -40% for the *R,S,S* enantiomer and -30% for gamma-cyhalothrin. These results in the orange matrix are probably the cause of the reproducibility values at 5 µg/kg and the area differences between both isomers in the calibration curves. Nevertheless, none of the results were above 50% and,

therefore, no strong matrix effects were observed in this study.

3.5. Field test

Two experiments were carried out in a greenhouse located in Almeria. Lettuces were planted in their grown stage and spiked with a commercial formulation containing the mixture of lambda- cyhalothrin enantiomers. The same experiment was repeated with metalaxyl in tomatoes. Following the DG SANTE/12682/2019 criteria [31], the parameters used to identify the pesticides were a retention time range of ± 0.1 min and the presence of two transitions that met the ion ratios. Concerning lambda-cyhalothrin, an equivalent degradation of both enantiomers was observed after 3, 7, 14, and 21 days following sample collection. The concentrations quantified were: 1497 and 1464 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 3, 953 and 914 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 7, 406 and 326 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 14, and 205 and 158 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 21 for the *R,S,S* and gamma enantiomers respectively. There were no great differences between the isomers concentrations. Lambda- cyhalothrin is a contact pesticide; its enantiomers did not seem to be affected differently by the environmental conditions present in the greenhouse. On the other hand, the concentrations of metalaxyl and its enantiomer metalaxyl-M (mefenoxam) in tomato were differently affected: 109 and 191 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 4, 93 and 176 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 7, 8 and 36 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 14, and 3 and 18 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ at day 21. Metalaxyl-M showed less degradation compared to its enantiomer; this is the most active isomer in the mixture due to its higher affinity to target receptors. While lambda-cyhalothrin is a contact pesticide, as previously mentioned, the metalaxyl mixture is a systemic pesticide. Metalaxyl enantiomers are absorbed by the plant and circulate through the plant's tissues, experiencing a different degradation during this process. Fig. 4. shows the significative degradation slope difference between the two enantiomers in the metalaxyl mixture.

4. Conclusions

Supercritical fluid chromatography in combination with cellulose polysaccharide columns, has been proven capable of performing fast, robust, and efficient separation of chiral pesticides. Following an examination of lambda-cyhalothrin and metalaxyl, it was found that their enantiomers could be identified at the 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ concentration level. These pesticides were also

evaluated in terms of linearity, reproducibility and matrix effects obtaining good results for each isomer. The greenhouse test allowed us to study of the degradation of each enantiomer. Lambda-cyhalothrin degradation in lettuce was the same for both isomers at different acute reference doses. However, metalaxyl-M (mefenoxam) degradation in tomato matrix was 2 to 6-times lower than its less active S- enantiomer. Supercritical fluid chromatography has shown itself to be a technique that provides good analytical results for chiral pesticide separation, even in complex cases.

Declaration of Competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Víctor Cutillas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Mar García-Valverde:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation. **María del Mar Gómez-Ramos:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Resources. **Francisco José Díaz-Galiano:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Carmen Ferrer:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Amadeo R. Fernández-Alba:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the funding support provided by the [European Commission](#), DG SANTE (Grant decision [SI2.802063](#)). The authors would also like to thank Shimadzu Corporation for providing the equipment and constant support of the work.

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Fig. 1. Chromatograms of the separation of lambda-cyhalothrin and metalaxyl using cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate) and amylose tris(3-chloro-5-methylphenylcarbamate).

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of the 21 pesticides of the multiresidue method separated using a polysaccharide cellulose column.

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of the 4 isomers that compose the Cyhalothrin mixture.

Fig. 4. Graphical representation showing the enantiomers concentration in the logarithm scale during the different days of sample collection after the pesticide application.

Table 1. RSD (%) obtained for metalaxyl and lambda-cyhalothrin enantiomers in all matrices analyzed at the lowest concentration level studied: 5 µg/kg (n = 5).

RSD (%) 5µg/kg	Metalaxyl			Lambda-cyhalothrin		
	Metalaxyl-M	S-enantiomer	SUM	Gamma	R,S,S-enantiomer	SUM
Tomato	6	5	5	7	6	6
Orange	4	12	6	6	4	4
Leek	9	6	7	12	13	11
Cayenne	5	3	4	12	9	9

Table 2. Matrix effects values of metalaxyl and lambda-cyhalothrin enantiomers for all the matrices studied.

M.E. (%)	Metalaxyl's			Lambda-cyhalothrin		
	Metalaxyl-M	S-Enantiomer	SUM	Gamma	R,S,S-Enantiomer	SUM
Tomato	4	1	2	-6	-11	-8
Orange	5	-1	2	-30	-40	-35
Leek	0	1	1	-27	-28	-28
Cayenne	5	3	4	16	12	14